

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

Educational communication and its relationship with school discipline in the classroom

Comunicación educativa y su relación con la disciplina escolar en el aula de clases

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Abstract This research aimed to identify the relationship between educational communication and school discipline in the classroom. It is important to highlight that indiscipline is a destructive behavior that does not promote peace and coexistence. The teacher's role is essential in the student's communication process. The methodology applied was a meta-analysis through a systematic review of different databases. The search criteria were titles related to the research, communicative education, and discipline in the classroom. With a descriptive review approach that positively influences the development of a strategy that strengthens teaching-learning. In the meta-analysis from the evaluation of 10 studies that included a total sample of 487 students. This analysis allowed us to demonstrate the existence of a high heterogeneity ($I^2 = 99.83\%$) and significance ($z = -0.8090$, $p = 0.4185$), so it can be stated that there is a correlation between the variables educational communication and discipline in the classroom. Measurement indicators such as respect for rules, conduct regulation, and frustration management were identified.

Keywords communication, education, discipline, students.

Resumen La presente investigación tuvo como objetivo, identificar la relación entre la comunicación educativa y la disciplina escolar en el aula. Es importante destacar que la indisciplina es un comportamiento destructivo que no promueve la paz y la convivencia. El rol que desempeña el docente es primordial en el proceso de comunicación de los estudiantes. La metodología aplicada fue un meta-análisis mediante la revisión sistemática en diferentes bases de datos. Los criterios de búsqueda fueron: título relacionado con la investigación, educación comunicativa y disciplina en el aula de clases. Con un enfoque de revisión descriptiva que influye de manera positiva en el desarrollo de una estrategia que fortalezca la enseñanza-aprendizaje. En el meta-análisis a partir de la evaluación de 10 estudios que incluyeron en total, una muestra de 487 estudiantes. Esto permitió demostrar la existencia de una heterogeneidad alta ($I^2 = 99,83\%$) y significativa ($z = -0,8090$, $p = 0,4185$), por lo que puede plantearse que existe una correlación entre las variables comunicación educativa y disciplina en el aula de clases. Se identificaron indicadores de medición como el respeto a las normas, regulación de la conducta y manejo de la frustración.

Palabras clave comunicación, educación, disciplina, estudiantes.

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Introduction

The United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) states that a priority strategy is the development of attitudes, values, and competencies conducive to establishing healthy and respectful relationships (UNESCO, 2022). The educational sector has been observed to lack the necessary tools to channel emotions (Fernández & Robles, 2018). Students tend to repress their opinions and emotions, resulting in inappropriate ways of expressing them, such as insults, shouting, physical aggression, irony, and sarcasm, which create a chaotic atmosphere in the classroom (Tanqueño, 2023).

The Ministry of Education of Ecuador has expressed that education policy requires a comprehensive approach, integrating cognitive and emotional skills and developing communication strategies to improve relationships between students and teachers. Addressing classroom discipline issues through behavioral and communication policies is also a key objective (Mineduc, 2020). Educational communication involves exchanging information and emotions that fosters transformation, encompassing elements such as the transmitted message, context, language, and the roles involved (Sardiñas et al., 2020).

The elements of educational communication include the teacher, the student, academic content, the channel for knowledge transmission, the processes of encoding information, and feedback to assess whether knowledge acquisition yields positive or negative outcomes (Narváez-Montoya, 2019). Educational communication involves providing resources and opportunities in the learning process and employing strategies, tools, and audiovisual materials to enhance knowledge comprehension.

One barrier to effective classroom discipline is adolescence, a stage in which students experience physical and emotional changes that shape their personalities (Iñaguazo, 2020). This period often coincides with social challenges such as parental divorce, substance abuse, risky sexual behaviors, and others, which influence adolescents' behavior. These challenges often manifest in rebellious attitudes toward authority in the classroom, stemming from frustration at not knowing how to manage these new experiences.

Classroom discipline is a significant element within teaching practices, as it facilitates the development of skills, abilities, and attitudes that require interpersonal relationships in the school environment (Álvarez, 2020). The teacher's role is pivotal in the communication process, carrying the responsibility of planning and implementing activities that benefit human relationships, starting from their perfor-

mance as a member and leader of the classroom. This effort promotes tolerance, camaraderie, and mutual respect under equal conditions for students.

Indiscipline is destructive behavior that undermines peace and coexistence in society. It is a pervasive issue in many nations, posing a threat to the lives of young people (Toala, 2020). Despite numerous efforts by global leaders to reduce this growing problem, especially in schools, indiscipline still needs to be addressed due to various factors that hinder its eradication.

Social factors influencing teacher-student relationships in schools include using social media, internet access, and violent video games (Candel, 2020). Consequently, it is crucial to seek strategies to create and promote a peaceful and harmonious work environment characterized by open and truthful communication based on mutual respect to counteract violence and disrespect among students and teachers.

Most teachers view themselves as mediators of inappropriate student behaviors in the classroom. They are interested in applying rules and activities that promote respect, communication, tolerance, and solidarity among students to prevent inappropriate conduct inside and outside the classroom (Sumari, 2021). Teacher training is essential for adopting and utilizing innovative tools to maintain discipline control during class sessions while fostering effective classroom management during pedagogical activities.

Adolescence, marked by physical and emotional changes essential to personality development, is a significant barrier to effective classroom discipline (Barida et al., 2021). Social challenges such as parental divorce, substance abuse, and risky sexual behaviors further compound this period, influencing adolescent behavior, which often manifests as rebellious attitudes toward authority in the classroom due to frustration with these new experiences.

Respect for rules is an established guideline that fosters community coexistence within an organization (Arguello, 2019). Adhering to rules promotes balance inside and outside workplaces, encourages order, and fosters new values—beyond respect—essential for proper school activities and life development.

Behavior regulation refers to how we express our thoughts and knowledge through different attitudes displayed in daily life (Chango, 2020). This behavior regulation involves performing tasks that demonstrate actions, ideas, or feelings, which require emotional self-control for regulation. Therefore, regulating behavior essentially controls our emotions in response to stimuli.

Managing frustration is an emotional response from psychological issues triggered by unexpected events or situations. It involves handling emotional reactions that arise when goals are not achieved (Espinoza, 2018). Discussing frustration highlights our capacity to manage emotions and reactions in the face of unexpected events that may disrupt our balance due to uncertainty about how to respond in such moments.

School discipline is a vital component of teaching practices, as it supports the development of skills, abilities, and attitudes requiring interpersonal relationships within the school environment (Álvarez, 2020). The teacher's role is central to the communication process, responsible for planning and executing activities that enhance human relationships, starting with their performance as a classroom member and leader. This effort fosters tolerance, camaraderie, and mutual respect among students under equal conditions. Considering this, the present study aimed to identify the relationship between educational communication and school discipline in the classroom.

Methodology

In this article, the databases Scopus, Web of Science, Scielo, and Google Scholar were consulted. The search criteria included titles related to the research, communicative education, and classroom discipline. A systematic review provided readers with an updated perspective on the relationship between communication and student discipline within the classroom. This descriptive review approach is particularly relevant in the field of education, offering valuable insights that can positively influence the development of strategies to strengthen the teaching-learning process.

To evaluate the association between educational communication and classroom discipline using the JAMOVI program, a 95% confidence interval was applied. Estimating the included studies' overall effects was obtained through random-effects models in cases with significant heterogeneity among studies. The heterogeneity of the studies was assessed using the I^2 statistic, which represents magnitudes of heterogeneity as follows: <25% low, 25-75% moderate, and >75% high. Statistical significance was defined as $p \leq 0.05$.

This study's limitations arose when evaluating various articles published in languages such as Portuguese or those requiring subscription for access. The eligibility criteria included titles related to the research topic, methodology, objectives, and results. A systematic review of scientific articles was carried out, as illustrated in the flowchart in Figure 1.

In the initial search, 52 articles were identified. After evaluating the full texts, 37 were excluded for containing information unrelated to the study's objective or being duplicate documents. Additionally, ten articles that met the inclusion criteria were selected by reporting information on the relationship between educational communication and classroom discipline.

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Figure 1. Flowchart of the systematic review and meta-analysis.

Results and discussion

Table 1 summarizes studies on student behavior conducted in various Latin American countries, highlighting characteristics such as methodology, study population, correlations, and evaluated criteria. In general, the studies involved student populations and employed descriptive and quantitative methodologies to analyze various behaviors in the educational setting.

Among the most notable investigations, several studies identified high correlations ($r = 0.9$) between respect for rules, behavior regulation, and frustration management with improvements in school coexistence (Espinoza, 2018; Fernández & Robles, 2018). On the other hand, some studies revealed lower correlations ($r = 0.2-0.3$), such as the association between family coexistence and school discipline (Sumari, 2021) or assertive communication and conflict resolution (Meza et al., 2019), suggesting a less direct relationship in these cases.

The evaluated criteria include respect for rules, emotional regulation, physical aggression, and punctuality. However, the findings also highlight persistent issues, such as inappro-

Table 1. Main characteristics of the articles included in the study

Reference	Country	N	Methodology	Study population	Correlation	Criteria
Álvarez (2020)	Panama	21	Non-experimental descriptive study	Students	0.9	Inappropriate behaviors, physical aggression, disrespectful language
Meza et al. (2022)	Ecuador	39	Quantitative study	Students	0.9	Attention in class, respect for teachers and peers, harmonious and peaceful relationships
Espinoza (2018)	Peru	136	Quantitative study	Students	0.9	Respect for rules, behavior regulation, frustration management
Toala et al. (2020)	Ecuador	185	Descriptive and quantitative study	Students	0.6	Punctuality, impassivity, inappropriate language, cellphone usage
Sumari (2021)	Peru	84	Descriptive and quantitative study	Students	0.2	Family coexistence, school discipline
Meza et al. (2019)	Ecuador	22	Quantitative study	Students	0.3	Aggression and conflicts, assertive communication
Candel (2020)	Ecuador	42	Descriptive and quantitative study	Students	0.6	Inappropriate behavior, challenging attitudes
Fernández & Robles (2018)	Peru	85	Quantitative study	Students	0.9	Vandalistic behavior, failure to meet responsibilities
Pin & Lescay (2020)	Ecuador	18	Descriptive and quantitative study	Students	0.8	Frustration management, impulsive and irritable attitude

appropriate cellphone use and challenging attitudes, particularly in contexts with lower institutional discipline (Toala et al., 2020; Candel, 2020). These data underscore the importance of a comprehensive approach in educational institutions to foster a harmonious and disciplined environment.

The characteristics of the studies included in the meta-analysis focused on the relationship between educational communication and classroom discipline. The studies were conducted between 2018 and 2021, with a combined sample size of 487 students. Most of the studies employed quantitative methodologies. The analysis examined the number of criteria used to evaluate the variables.

In the meta-analysis (Figure 2), based on the evaluation of 10 studies, high heterogeneity was demonstrated ($I^2 = 99.83\%$) and was significant ($z = -0.8090$, $p = 0.4185$). The mean difference based on the random effects model was -3.8442 (95% CI: -13.1572 to 5.4688). Therefore, although the average estimated outcome is positive, the actual result may be harmful in some studies.

An examination of the standardized residuals revealed that

none of the studies had a value greater than ± 2.8070 , indicating no outliers in this model. According to Cook's distances, none of the studies could be considered overly influential. Neither the rank correlation nor the regression test indicated any asymmetry in the funnel plot ($p = 0.7194$ and $p = 0.4903$, respectively).

The meta-analysis results determined a high effect in the correlation between the variables of educational communication and classroom discipline. The systematic review of studies on the variables of interest identified measurement indicators such as inappropriate behaviors, physical aggression, disrespectful words, attention in class, respect for the teacher and peers, harmonious and peaceful relationships, respect for rules, behavior regulation, and frustration management. These indicators allow for the evaluation of educational communication and discipline in the classroom, providing insight into whether a good relationship exists between the teacher and students.

Figure 2. Meta-analysis of the therapeutic effect of honey on healing in minor species.

Conclusions

School discipline is considered the student’s behavior within the classroom, assessed based on parameters such as respect for rules, behavior regulation, and frustration management. It is necessary for the harmonious development of teaching-learning activities in the classroom and also contributes to optimal communication between teachers and students. The role of the teacher is crucial in the communicational process, as they are responsible for planning and executing activities that benefit human relationships, starting from their role as a member and leader of the classroom. It is a significant element carried out within the teaching action, as it involves the development of skills, abilities, and attitudes that require interpersonal relationships within the school environment. Respect for rules within the classroom is not developed optimally; furthermore, the actions applied in behavior regulation need to be improved, preventing discipline from being established in the classroom. In terms of frustration management, emotional control is not achieved, leading to a tense atmosphere.

References

Álvarez, A.M. (2020). Orientación para docentes de educación básica para fortalecer la disciplina escolar. *Conrado*, 16(76), 453-458. http://scielo.sld.cu/scielo.php?script=sci_arttext&pid=S1990-86442020000500453&lng=es&tlng=es

Barida, M., Hidayah, N., Mappiare, A., Ramli, M., & Taufiq, A. (2021). Development of an Instrument of Assertive Communication Scale Based on Yogyakarta

Cultural Value. *Pegem Journal of Education and Instruction*, 11(4), 100-109. <https://doi.org/10.47750/pegegog.11.04.10>

Candel, R.P. (2020). *Liderazgo docente en la disciplina escolar de los estudiantes de la de la Unidad Educativa Elías Rivero Góngora, Guayaquil 2020*. Universidad César Vallejo. <https://repositorio.ucv.edu.pe/handle/20.500.12692/52481>

Chango, M. (2020). La incidencia de nuevas estrategias comunicacionales y su aplicación en la educación de tercer nivel en tiempos de pandemia en la Universidad Técnica de Babahoyo durante el período mayo - agosto 2020. Obtenido de Google académico: <http://dspace.utb.edu.ec/bitstream/handle/49000/8791/E-UTB-FCJSE-CSO-CIAL-000298.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

Espinoza, C.P. (2018). *Estilos parentales y disciplina escolar en estudiantes de secundaria, institución educativa José Abelardo Quiñones González - Los Olivos, 2018*. Universidad César Vallejo. https://repositorio.ucv.edu.pe/bitstream/handle/20.500.12692/27620/Espinoza_ICP.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y

Fernández, J., & Robles, R. (2018). *Estrategias conductuales para mejorar la disciplina escolar en los alumnos del tercer y cuarto grado de educación primaria en la Institución educativa 16608 de Misquiyacu alto, Cajaruro Utucubamba Amazonas*. Universidad César Vallejo. <https://repositorio.ucv.edu.pe/handle/20.500.12692/33356>

Iñaguazo, H.P. (2020). La relación entre la comunicación interna y el clima laboral en los docentes de la unidad educativa San Joaquín, de la parroquia Cumbe, en el

- periodo 2018. *Ciencia y educación*, 1(2), 6-17. <https://doi.org/10.48169/Ecuatesis/0102202007>
- Meza, D.M., Meza, H.L., Vera, J.L., Sabando, A.R., Arguello, A.M., & Meza, A.M. (2022). Influencia del comportamiento escolar en el rendimiento académico de los estudiantes en la educación a distancia-virtual. *Revista Cognosis*, VII(4), 107-124. <https://revistas.utm.edu.ec/index.php/Cognosis/article/download/4890/5724/22665>
- Meza, D.M., Obaco, E.E., & Cedeño, C.A. (2019). Disciplina escolar y rendimiento académico: análisis correlacional. *Mundo recursivo*, 2(1), 111-128. <https://www.atlantic.edu.ec/ojs/index.php/mundor/article/view/34>
- MINEDUC. (2020). *Plan Educativo Sección 5: Socio emocional*. Obtenido de Ministerio de Educación del Ecuador. https://educacion.gob.ec/wp-content/uploads/downloads/2020/09/Seccion-5_Socioemocional.pdf
- Narvárez-Montoya, A. (2019). Comunicación educativa, educomunicación y educación mediática: una propuesta de investigación y formación desde un enfoque culturalista. *Palabra Clave*, 22(3), e22311. <https://doi.org/10.5294/pacla.2019.22.3.11>
- Pin, T.B., & Lescay, D.M. (2020). El valor de la disciplina en el proceso de formación de los estudiantes de educación básica. *Revista Cognosis*, 5, 01-18. <https://doi.org/10.33936/cognosis.v5i0.2285>
- Sardiñas, Y., Domínguez, I., & Reinoso, C.B. (2020). La comunicación educativa: su desarrollo en el profesor de secundaria básica. *Revista Científico Metodológica*, (71), 18-74. http://scielo.sld.cu/scielo.php?script=sci_arttext&pid=S1992-82382020000200018
- Sumari, F.R. (2021). Convivencia familiar y disciplina escolar en estudiantes de tercer grado de secundaria de la institución educativa Horacio Zeballos Gamez, Madre de Dios-2020. Universidad Nacional de San Agustín de Arequipa. <https://repositorio.unsa.edu.pe/items/7f981991-af34-4a85-86bf-3e1f352712b3>
- Tanqueño, K.L. (2023). Gestión institucional y las estrategias de comunicación en una unidad educativa de Guayaquil, 2022. Universidad César Vallejo. https://repositorio.ucv.edu.pe/bitstream/handle/20.500.12692/106856/Tanque%c3%b1o_GKL-SD.pdf?sequence=4&isAllowed=y
- Toala, S.R., Quiñónez, E.C., & Gómez, L.Y. (2020). La indisciplina y sus factores en la enseñanza aprendizaje. *Psychology Research*, 3(1), 21-38. <https://doi.org/10.33000/mlspr.v2i2.392>
- UNESCO. (2022). *Estrategia de comunicación orientada a las Naciones Unidas sobre la comunicación en materia de igualdad de género en y a través de la educación*. Obtenido de Organización de las Naciones Unidas para la Educación, la Ciencia y la Cultura. <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000380973>

Conflicts of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

Author contributions

Diana Ganchozo: Conceptualization, data curation, research, methodology, writing the original draft, writing, review and editing.

Data availability statement

The datasets used and/or analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

Statement on the use of AI

The authors acknowledge the use of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies to improve the readability and clarity of the article.

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